

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Abstract. *This article presents productive, modern and innovative methods of teaching English, in order to get learners more interested in learning English in primary classes.*

Keywords: *mixed technique, interesting games, primary classes, modern and innovative methods, pantomime.*

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, the interest of young people in learning foreign languages increased, and many opportunities for language learning are created by our country. As our first president, Islam Karimov, said: "Currently, the teaching of foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, which is striving to take its rightful place in the world community, and for our nation, which is building its great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners." Especially in primary education. One of the decisions that led to positive changes is the Decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of foreign languages" dated December 10, 2012. According to this decision, to teach languages, mainly English from primary school, to further increase their interest in learning foreign languages, to teach English classes from 1st grade in all general education schools in the form of various interesting games and at the same time, the development of students' oral speech, and from the 2nd grade, the gradual transition to modern, innovative methods of teaching the alphabet, reading and grammar began. Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing. This is because it is becoming more and more difficult to live without knowing English in the course of life. But language learning also depends on age. In fact,

scientists have proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, the fact that children have more time than adults, and they keep the learned information in their memory quickly.

DISCUSSION

As Masaru Ibuka, one of the Chinese inventors, wrote in his famous book "After that it's too late": "...a child's brain can hold an infinite amount of information...". It should also be noted that children of 6-7 years old do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. That is why it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language, it can tire the child and weaken his interest in learning the language. Because teaching a foreign language to elementary school students is difficult and at the same time it is one of the responsible tasks. That's why the following innovative methods can be used to teach English language meaningfully and interestingly to elementary school students:

- Remembering by sight. It is known that young children remember things they see more than what they hear. Therefore, teaching new words through various visual aids, posters, visible and commonly used things in everyday life, teaching new words and making sentences with the new words learned. . For example, writing on a book, table, blackboard, pen, window, etc. Since such things are often seen and used in everyday life, the child learns these words involuntarily.
- Sing words that are hard to understand or remember to music through songs and poems. In addition to remembering new words, the child's speech also develops. For example, it can be shown that children learning the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing.
- TO includes many competitive grammar and vocabulary games. In this, children perform various tasks given by the teacher. As a result, competition will arise among students, and their interest in learning the language will increase. After all, as Chinese thinkers say: "All human interests arise through competition."
- Mixed technique here we can optionally combine different techniques. For example, children can play games, sing songs, draw pictures, show new words through various actions. The advantage of the technique is diversity. In this, the reader is not limited by only one thing.
- Teaching through cartoons. It is known that children are interested in watching different cartoons. In the process of watching cartoons in English, although he does

not understand the words in the cartoon, he tries to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- Learning through fun games; The role of teaching English through various games is incomparable. Playing various games during the lesson will increase the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom and encourage inactive students to participate better in the lessons. The following games can be an example of our word.
- "Merry Riddles" Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle.
- "Pantomime" (pantomime). In this, the teacher tells the students a word and the student shows it. The rest of the students will have to find the word and say its English name.
- Learning through senses (tasting vegetables, fruits, food, holding various objects, smelling flowers). Before studying this new method, it is necessary to quote the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "The teacher, who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory, should use as many of the child's sensory organs as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations and it should even try to involve the senses of smell and taste in the process of remembering".

THE RESULT

In fact, language learning through the senses is more useful and effective than other methods. For example, in the process of tasting a single apple, the student knows its color, taste, size, smell, and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children the English name of the colors, the children immediately remember the time when they ate the fruit. Therefore, the use of such methods helps the student to retain information in his memory for a long time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teaching language to elementary school students is not a duty, but rather, using interesting games and innovative methods, can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, as the educational system also sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will better develop ways to effectively use innovative technologies. we can contribute.

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